

MAGNESIUM ALLOY ELEKTRON21 REINFORCED WITH ALN: PROCESSING, MICROSTRUCTURE AND COMPRESSION CREEP RESPONSE

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ABSTRACT

The development of high performance aluminium and magnesium based materials is a subject investigated within the European Commission project ExoMet, that started in the summer of 2012. Novel grain refining and nanoparticle addition in combination with physical melt treatment using external fields is expected to improve mechanical properties of aluminium and magnesium alloys in terms of strength and ductility, but also creep resistance. External fields applied during mixing are electromagnetic, ultrasonic, and mechanical. In this study, magnesium alloy Elektron21 was melted and AlN nanoparticles were added to the melt. The melt was mixed by simultaneously applying mechanical and ultrasonic stirring to avoid agglomeration. A modified permanent mould indirect chill casting process was selected for casting the materials, because this process results in very dense casting, free of pores and blowholes. The resulting materials were examined by metallography, electron microscopy, hardness, compression creep and mechanical compression strength methods. Microstructure investigation, including TEM, shows that most of the AlN-particles are pushed in the intermetallic phase (i.e. in interdendritic regions) during solidification, whereas few of them are trapped in the magnesium-matrix, not far from the intermetallic regions. Compression creep tests at a temperature of 240 °C and constant stresses between 70 and 200 MPa were performed and the minimum creep rate was determined from these tests. Comparison of creep rates of nanocomposite and unreinforced alloy Elektron21 show that the addition of 1 wt.-% AlN nanoparticles improves creep strength significantly. From the results stress exponents are calculated to obtain information about the rate controlling deformation mechanisms during creep.

1 INTRODUCTION

For several years ceramic nanoparticles have been commercially available and their costs have decreased significantly. After magnesium based composites with short fibre or micro sized particle reinforcements were investigated already in the 1980s, nanoparticle reinforcement has also come into focus in recent years, due to the fact that only a small amount of particles has the ability to improve mechanical properties significantly. This is true, not only for mechanical strength, but also for ductility, which usually exclude each other. The strengthening effect is mainly due to their ideal size for Orowan strengthening under the precondition that they are well distributed in the magnesium matrix. Nanoparticles act as obstacles for the motion of dislocation because they are non-shearable. Other strengthening effects, such as load transfer, Hall-Petch strengthening and CTE mismatch are comparatively minor to the Orowan strengthening of nanoparticles. An overview of nanoparticle-reinforced magnesium alloys in terms of mechanical properties and processes for particle introduction

into the matrix is given in [1]. During the preparation of the composites it is possible that reactions occur, since magnesium is a very reactive metal, even between alloying elements and nanoparticles. These reactions can modify the composition, size and shape of the nanoparticles, and can have an influence on their dispersion and interface properties [2].

The aim of this work is to investigate the influence of the addition of AlN nanoparticles to the magnesium alloy Elektron21 on the microstructure and mechanical properties, both at room and high temperatures. With that purpose, the Elektron21 alloy with and without AlN nanoparticles was carefully processed by ultrasound assisted stirring.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

Materials processing

Magnesium alloy Elektron21 was molten and temperature was kept constant at 720 °C. A cylindrical mould, preheated to 450 °C was filled with melt and put into a three zone resistance furnace for keeping the temperature constant at 670 °C. A constant flux of cover gas (Ar + 1% SF₆) was applied for the treatment time. AlN nanoparticles were added at 1 wt.-%, stirred (200 rpm) and additionally the power ultrasound was applied for 5 minutes at 0.3 kW. After the sonication the mould with the melt was lowered into a water bath located beneath the ring furnace. Since the mould descended at a constant speed into the water bath, the solidification started at the bottom of the mould. This process is described in [3] and it results in a very dense casting, because the remaining melt is always above the solidified material, which leads to shrinkage feeding at every point. The ultrasound equipment used is shown in Figure 1. It consists of an ultrasound generator UIP1500hd made by Hielscher company with a frequency of 20 kHz and a maximum power of 1.5 kW. The sonotrode is made of titanium. For comparison, the same material was prepared without adding AlN, but with applying all the stirring and ultrasound to the melt.

Fig 1: Ultrasound generator (left) with attached booster and sonotrode

Metallography and Hardness

For the microstructural investigation, samples were cut from the casted cylinders. Each sample was embedded in resin, grinded (800, 1200, and 2500 grit), polished (1 μm diamond paste in ethanol) and etched (9% picric acid solution). Hardness tests were executed with an EMCO MIC 010 machine according to the HV5 test standard.

Compression Strength

The compression strength tests were run on a Zwick tensile and compression strength testing machine. Samples were cut by spark erosion and their dimensions were 15 mm in length and 10 mm in diameter.

Compression Creep

Cylinders with a length of 15 mm and a diameter of 6 mm were cut from both materials using spark erosion technique. Compression creep tests were performed at 240 °C and constant stresses between 70 MPa and 200 MPa at lever arm testing systems from ATS. Deformation over time was recorded and the first derivative was calculated to find the minimum creep rate $\dot{\epsilon}_s$.

SEM and TEM Characterizations

Samples for transmission electron microscopy (TEM) observations were prepared from 3 mm diameter disks (average thickness of 150 μm) followed by mechanical grinding with a Dimpler and finally by ion milling at room temperature (final energy of Ar ions set to 1.5 keV). Microstructural

characterization of the composite was carried out in TEM mode with a JEOL JEM 2010 operating at 200 kV and equipped with a LaB6 filament. Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy (STEM) in High Angle Annular Dark Field (HAADF) mode and coupled with EDS mapping was done with a JEOL ARM 200 F operating at 200 kV. This microscope is both equipped with a Schottky field emitter and a Cs-corrector of the electron probe.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Metallography and Hardness

Pictures of the microstructure of the materials are shown below in Fig. 2. The unreinforced Elektron21 shows globular grains with an average grain size of 80.1 μm . After nanoparticle addition grains appear more dendritic and average grain size is reduced to 74.1 μm . Table 1 shows the grain size measurements as well as the hardness results. It appears that hardness is not affected by the addition and grain size seems to be slightly reduced with the incorporation of the nanoparticles.

Figure 2: Optical microscopy pictures. a) Elektron21 and b) Elektron21 with AlN addition.

<i>Material</i>	<i>Grain size [μm]</i>	<i>Hardness (HV5)</i>
Elektron21	80.1 \pm 39.4	47.9 \pm 2.1
Elektron21 + 1wt.-% AlN	74.1 \pm 32.5	48.1 \pm 2.5

Table 1: Grain size and hardness measurements

Compression Strength

Results of room temperature compression tests can be seen in the table 2. Compression strength is not affected in a noticeable way by the addition of the nanoparticles.

<i>Material</i>	<i>UCS [MPa]</i>	<i>CYS [MPa]</i>	<i>E [%]</i>
Elektron21	316.8 \pm 1.5	92.4 \pm 0.8	21.6 \pm 0.8
Elektron21 + 1wt.-% AlN	315.7 \pm 0.8	88.0 \pm 1.0	22.1 \pm 0.6

Table 2: Results of compression tests at room temperature

Creep

Creep curves of compression creep tests performed at 240 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and stresses between 70 and 200 MPa were differentiated in order to evaluate the minimum creep rate. Fig 3a shows creep curves of creep deformation over time of Elektron21 and Elektron21 + 1 wt.-% AlN from creep tests at 240 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 140 MPa. Fig. 3b shows the first derivative of the creep curves, the creep rate over time from which the minimum creep rate can be seen, and Fig 3c shows the creep rate over the creep deformation.

Fig 3: a) creep curves of Elektron21 and Elektron21+1 wt.-% AlN, b) creep rate over time and c) creep rate over creep deformation.

The Norton-Arrhenius equation (Eq. 1) describes the dependence of minimum creep rate $\dot{\epsilon}_s$ on temperature T and applied stress σ .

$$\dot{\epsilon}_s = \frac{ADGb}{kT} \left(\frac{\sigma}{G} \right)^n \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

where A is a material dependent constant, G the shear modulus, b the Burgers vector, k the Boltzmann constant and n the stress exponent, which gives information about the rate-controlling deformation mechanisms during creep. D is the diffusion coefficient, and this can be expressed as:

$$D = D_0 \cdot \exp\left[-\frac{Q_c}{RT}\right], \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

where D_0 is the frequency factor and Q_c the apparent activation energy for creep. The stress exponent n can be determined by plotting the minimum creep rates in a double logarithmic creep rate and stress field.

Fig 4 shows this plot. At low stresses up to 120 MPa the stress exponent n is 4.8 and 5.0 for Elektron21 and Elektron21+AlN, respectively. At higher stresses it is 6.6 and 8.3. The AlN- reinforced Elektron21 shows at all applied stresses lower minimum creep rate compared to the unreinforced. The difference decreases with increasing stress.

Fig 4: Double logarithmic plot of minimum creep rate versus applied stress from tests performed at 240°C.

A threshold stress concept or back stress concept was described for particle or precipitate strengthened alloys. Elektron21 is such an alloy. It is precipitate strengthened by Mg-RE precipitates. Addition of nanoparticles improves obviously the creep resistance; therefore the threshold stress concept can be applied as well. Interaction of dislocations and precipitates or particles is assumed to be the origin of the threshold stress, but different explanations exist. Three of them are listed here:

- An additional stress, that is needed to bow dislocations between the precipitates or particles, called Orowan stress [4, 5, 6]
- The stress required to detach a dislocation from an obstacle [7, 8]
- The additional back stress required to climb over an obstacle [9].

For the introduction of a threshold stress σ_{thr} into the calculation, Eq. 1 is usually modified in a way that the effective stress σ_{eff} replaces the applied stress σ .

$$\sigma_{eff} = \sigma - \sigma_{thr} \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

and so giving Eq. 4

$$\dot{\epsilon}_s = \frac{ADGb}{kT} \left(\frac{\sigma_{eff}}{G} \right)^{n_t} \quad . \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

The true stress exponent n_t is calculated based on the concept of a threshold stress. According to experimental data, Li and Langdon developed a method to calculate the threshold stress from minimum creep rates of tests at a certain temperature and different stresses [10]. The lowest measurable minimum creep rate was determined to be 10^{-10} s^{-1} , which corresponds to a deformation of only 1% in three years. An extrapolation of double logarithmic plots of $\dot{\epsilon}_s$ over the applied stress σ to a value of 10^{-10} s^{-1} gives the threshold stress σ_{thr} . The calculated values for σ_{thr} are 10.7 and 31.0 for Elektron21 and Elektron21+AlN, respectively. That is a huge difference, which seems to be due to the addition of nanoparticles. Minimum creep rates can be plotted over the calculated effective stresses and slopes are now giving the true stress exponents n_t . They are 4.2 and 3.3 for Elektron21 and Elektron21+AlN respectively, at stresses below 120 MPa as shown in Fig 5. At higher stresses true stress exponents cannot be calculated due to the differences in stress exponents at those higher applied stresses (see Fig 4).

Fig 5: Minimum creep rates over effective stress

After applying the concept of threshold stress, the true stress exponents n_t are in a range that fits to the theoretical assumptions concerned with the deformation mechanisms. A value of $n=3$ is related to the viscous glide of dislocations being the rate controlling deformation mechanism [11, 12, 13], $n=5$ is related to dislocation climbing at high temperatures being the rate controlling deformation mechanism during creep [11, 12, 14].

SEM and TEM Characterizations

After casting, the microstructure is composed of magnesium matrix dendrites (designated as “Mg-grains”) and interdendritic areas where the eutectic reaction has led to a phase separation between a magnesium and an intermetallic phase (enriched in rare-earth elements). Fig. 6 shows a BF-TEM image of a Mg-grain in the EL21+AlN composite, where a large amount of rare-earth containing precipitates is observed. These precipitates vary in size and shape. Their homogeneous distribution in the matrix suggests that they play a major role in the hindering of dislocation motion.

TEM investigations revealed that few AlN particles were found in the Mg-grains. First of all, it

must be pointed out that aluminium was identified in the intermetallic phase of eutectic regions. This confirms that the residual Al found in the AlN powder was dissolved in the melt during casting. Fig. 7 shows a BF-TEM image of a eutectic region where aluminium was detected. Second, many AlN particles are observed but they are mainly found in the eutectic regions or in Mg-grains close to the eutectic regions.

Fig. 6: Bright Field (BF)-TEM image of EL21+AlN composite showing a large number density of rare-earth containing precipitates.

Fig. 7: (a) BF-TEM image showing a eutectic region with locations of aluminum dissolved in the intermetallic phase. (b) Composition determined by EDS at location B.

Fig. 8 shows a BF-TEM image of few AlN particles unambiguously identified by EDS. In this image, AlN particles are agglomerated in the eutectic region, which implies that particles were pushed by the solidification front. However the EDS analysis shows an important amount of zirconium, which may imply a partial reaction between the AlN particles and zirconium. Indeed, the reactivity between zirconium and AlN is well known in the literature, for instance in the Al-Zr alloys, where Zr is added to the Al to improve the wettability of Al on AlN thanks to the formation of a ZrN layer at the interface [15, 16]. Other researchers [17] suggest that aluminides $ZrAl_3$ and $ZrAl_2$ form at the Zr/Al interface.

Fig.9 shows a BF-TEM of AlN particles and the EDS analysis of one of these particles. Besides the

presence of zirconium we can observe on the edges of AlN particles a dark phase. In order to identify the composition of these phases on the AlN surface, an EDS mapping was performed.

Fig. 10a is a STEM-HAADF image of a region where some AlN particles are gathered. This region was investigated by STEM EDS, results are indicated in Fig. 10b.

Fig. 8: (a) BF-TEM image of AlN particles, (b) Typical EDS spectrum of an AlN particle.

Fig. 9: (a) BF-TEM image of AlN particles, (b) EDS spectrum of an AlN particle.

From the EDS mapping, it can be confirmed that a reaction evolved between AlN particles and Zr on the particles' surface. The Al detected in the intermetallic region thus derived not only from the residual Al in the AlN particles, but also from this reaction, during which some Al may be released from the AlN particles. TEM observations clearly reveal that AlN particles are mostly present in eutectic regions or in Mg-grains very close to these regions. As a consequence, we suspect a dragging effect which could lead to a reduction of the speed of the solidification front and, in the end, to a smaller size of Mg-grains. From a microstructural point of view, the better mechanical behaviour revealed for this composite may result from two effects: i) a grain size reduction produced by a dragging effect of AlN particles during solidification; ii) a composite effect in the eutectic regions,

where AlN particles are expected to play their role of reinforcement.

Insofar as the specimen investigated in TEM had been submitted to creep, dislocations have also been observed in a mode close to weak beam condition in dark field (DF) (Fig.11). Basal slip has been revealed by the observation of bright linear contrast along the trace of (0002) planes of magnesium. Many bright contrasts reveal a large amount of dislocations, even in the vicinity of AlN particles. However, observations could not reveal the actual influence of AlN particles on the dislocations. This work would require a more detailed investigation. In addition, it is clear that the impact of AlN on dislocation motion in Mg-grains is by far negligible as compared to the influence of rare-earth containing precipitates, whose number density in Mg-grains is much larger.

Fig. 10: (a) STEM-HAADF image showing AlN particles, (b) EDX mapping of location A

Fig. 11: DF-TEM image obtained along $\mathbf{z} = [11-20]$ with $\mathbf{g} = [-1100]$. The corresponding diffraction pattern is shown in the inset. White arrows show the location of AlN particles (in dark contrast for these imaging conditions).

4 CONCLUSIONS

Magnesium alloy Elektron21 was reinforced with AlN nanoparticles, the melt was processed with mechanical and ultrasonic stirring and casted following a modified permanent mould indirect chill casting process. The microstructure of the materials was examined through optical microscopy as well as SEM and TEM characterization, and they were tested for their properties using hardness, compression strength and compression creep tests. The metallography showed a slight decrease of the grain size after the addition of the nanoparticles, also the shape of the grains was affected, from globular in the unreinforced, to resembling a more dendritic structure after the addition. Hardness and compression strength did not seem to be affected by the presence of AlN nanoparticles. The compression creep results appear to improve when the alloy is reinforced, affecting both the minimum creep rates, as well as the stress exponents. The threshold stresses, which are 10.7 for Elektron21 and 31.0 for Elektron21+AlN, differ significantly. According to the calculations for the stress exponents the rate controlling deformation mechanisms are viscous glide of dislocations and dislocation climbing. In the TEM investigations it was found that few AlN particles were present inside the grains. The residual Al from the AlN powder was found in the intermetallic phase of the eutectic regions, where also AlN particles are mainly located as well as in magnesium grains close to the eutectic regions, pushed there by the solidification front. The improved creep behaviour may be explained by i) either the reduction of the grain size that was caused by the dragging effect of AlN particles during solidification, ii) or a composite effect in the eutectic regions. It was not possible to explain the influence of the AlN particles on the dislocations, something that requires further investigation, and the effects of AlN on dislocation motion in magnesium grains seem to be negligible compared to those from rare-earth precipitates.

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